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Energy Management System Skills Required For Employability Of Electrical Technology Education Graduates In The Industries In Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the energy management system skills required for the employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was adopted, and a structured questionnaire was administered to 80 respondents, comprising 40 electrical industry managers and 40 supervisors. The results show that system design skills, system installation skills, and system troubleshooting and maintenance skills are essential for the employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries. The study also found no significant difference between the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the required skills. Based on the findings the study recommended that: Industries should provide opportunities for Electrical Technology Education students to gain practical experience in system troubleshooting and maintenance, Universities offering Electrical Technology Education programs should review and revise their curricula to ensure that they are providing students with the necessary skills and knowledge in system design and Educational institutions offering Electrical Technology Education in Rivers State should incorporate practical training and hands-on experience in energy management systems into their curricula.

Keywords: Energy Management System, Employability, Electrical Technology Education, System Design Skills

INTRODUCTION

The global energy landscape is undergoing a significant transformation, driven by the increasing demand for sustainable and efficient energy solutions (International Energy Agency, 2020). As a result, the importance of effective energy management systems has become paramount, necessitating the development of skilled professionals who can design, implement, and maintain these systems (United Nations, 2020). The energy sector is becoming increasingly complex, with a growing focus on renewable energy, energy efficiency, and sustainability (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2020). This shift towards sustainable energy solutions requires a workforce with specialized skills and knowledge in energy management, including energy auditing, renewable energy systems, and energy monitoring and control which can be effectively developed through university education.

University education, particularly in Electrical Technology Education (ETE) program, plays a critical role in equipping students with the requisite knowledge, skills, and competencies to address the complex energy challenges facing the world today (Alaoui & Wang, 2019). These program provide students with a comprehensive understanding of electrical systems, energy management and sustainable technologies. This comprehensive education prepares them for careers in the energy sector. However, despite the critical importance of energy management many Electrical Technology Education graduates lack the necessary skills and competencies to effectively manage energy systems and promote sustainable development. This skills gap is attributed to various factors, including inadequate curriculum design, insufficient practical training, and limited exposure to industry practices. Consequently, ETE graduates typically need supplementary training and professional development to stay competitive in the industry and make a significant impact on the transition to sustainable energy solutions. The global energy market is expected to continue growing, with the International Energy Agency (2020) predicting a 30% increase in global energy demand by 2040. This growth will require significant investments in energy infrastructure, including renewable energy systems, energy storage, and smart grids (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2020). To meet this growing demand, the energy sector requires skilled professionals who can design, install, troubleshoot, and maintain energy management systems, ensuring the efficient, reliable, and sustainable operation of energy infrastructure (United Nations, 2020).

Energy management system design skill refers to the ability to plan, design, and test energy management systems that meet specific requirements and specifications (Hawkes et al., 2013). This skill is essential for energy management professionals, as it enables them to create efficient, reliable, and high-performance energy systems (Igrubia et al., 2021). It involves creating and assembling networks of energy management components to perform desired functions. In energy management systems, electrical circuit design plays a crucial role in maximizing the efficiency of energy conversion and storage (Muhammed, 2018). Designers often use specialized components like energy harvesting modules, power management ICs, and energy storage devices such as super capacitors or rechargeable batteries to capture and store harvested energy effectively (Charle, 2020). Electrical technology education graduates must learn how to design electrical circuits, select appropriate components, and ensure the system meets safety and efficiency standards, ultimately acquiring the necessary installation skills.

Installation skills refer to the technical competencies and expertise required to physically implement and integrate energy management systems, including the mounting, wiring, and configuration of various components, such as solar panels, wind turbines, batteries, and other equipment (Muhammed, 2018). These skills involve a comprehensive understanding of electrical and mechanical systems, as well as the ability to ensure compliance with relevant safety standards, regulations, and codes (Charle, 2020). Effective installation skills are critical for ensuring the safe, efficient, and reliable operation of energy management systems, and are therefore a vital component of the technical expertise required of energy management professionals, ultimately complementing Troubleshooting and maintenance skills.

Troubleshooting and maintenance skills are essential in energy management systems, as they involve analyzing, detecting, and resolving problems with equipment, systems, or processes, as well as performing routine maintenance tasks to prevent future problems (Hawkes et al., 2013). This involves diagnosing faults, repairing faulty components, and improving system efficiency. Troubleshooting and maintenance skills require a combination of technical knowledge, logical reasoning, and problem-solving abilities to diagnose the root cause of malfunctions and implement effective solutions. Effective maintenance is critical in energy management systems, as it involves the combination of all actions carried out to service, repair or replace a device or system so that it will continue to operate satisfactorily for a specified period (Igrubia et al., 2021). The objectives of maintenance in energy management systems include improving system reliability, decreasing maintenance costs, decreasing the number of maintenance operations, and reducing human error influences (Charle, 2020). This study aims to investigate the energy management system skills required for the employability of Electrical Technology Education (ETE) graduates in the industry, focusing on the acquisition of Energy Management System Design skills, Installation skills, knowledge of Renewable Energy Systems, and Troubleshooting and Maintenance skills. Additionally, the study seeks to identify emerging trends and technologies in the

energy sector, and the corresponding skills and competencies required of ETE graduates to remain competitive and address these trends effectively.

Statement of Problem

The increasing demand for energy management systems in various industries has created a need for skilled professionals who can design, install, and maintain these systems (Hawkes et al., 2013). However, a growing concern exists that Electrical Technology Education (ETE) graduates in Rivers State, Nigeria, may not possess the requisite energy management system skills required for employability in the industries (Muhammed, 2018). This skill gap may hinder the ability of ETE graduates to secure employment, thereby affecting their career prospects and the overall development of the energy sector in the state (Igrubia et al., 2021). Furthermore, the lack of energy management system skills may also impact the efficiency, safety, and reliability of energy systems in industries, ultimately affecting the economy and environment (Charle, 2020). Therefore, this study aims to investigate the energy management system skills required for the employability of ETE graduates in the industries in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to investigate energy management system skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria. Specifically the study sought to examine the energy management system:

1. design skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria
2. Installation skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria
3. troubleshooting and maintenance skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria

Research questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. what are the system design skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria
2. what are the system installation skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria
3. what are the system troubleshooting and maintenance skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria

Hypothesis

The following Null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance:

HO₁: There is no significant deference between the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system design skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria

HO₂: There is no significant deference between the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system installation skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria

HO₃: There is no significant deference between the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system troubleshooting and maintenance skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

The study adopts a descriptive survey. This design was appropriate for the study because survey design is a type of descriptive survey research whose purpose is to collect data from a large or manageable sample of a population, so as to define the distribution, happening and interaction of educational and sociological occurrences. A descriptive survey design was deemed relevant and suitable for this study, as it aided the collection of data through questionnaires administered to electrical industry managers and supervisors, providing insights into the energy management system skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state. The study was carried out in Rivers State,

Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of 80 respondents, comprising 40 electrical industry managers and 40 supervisors from 40 industries in Rivers State. The study made use of purposive sampling techniques. A Structured questionnaire titled: Energy Management System Skills required for Employability of Graduates (EMSSEQ), was used for data collection. The questionnaire was sub-divided into four (4) segments, such as A, B and C, respectively, The items questionnaire Highly Extent was structured on 5 point Likert scales of Strongly Agree (SA) – 5, Agree (A) – 4, Undecided (UD) – 3, Disagree (D) – 2, Strongly Disagree (SD) – 1. The instrument, EMSSEQ was face-validated by three experts, two from Department of. Industrial Technical Education Ignatius Ajuru University of education Port Harcourt and the other one from Department of Electrical/Electronic Engineering Technology, Ken Sarowiwa Polytechnic, Rivers State. Cronbach Alpha reliability method was adopted to determine the internal consistency of the questionnaire items and .85 was obtained as the overall reliability coefficient. Eighty (80) copies of the 30 items questionnaire were administered by the researchers on the respondents. One hundred percent 100% of the administered questionnaires were retrieved and analyzed. The computation of the mean, standard deviation and t-test was carried out with Statistical Package for Social Science version 23.10 (SPSS). To answer research questions 1,2 and 3 questionnaire items within mean scores of 3.50 and above was uphold and questionnaire items within mean scores of 3.49 and below was rejected. the decision for null hypotheses was as follows: if the calculated value of the (t- cal) was less than the critical value of (t-crit), accept the null hypothesis but if the calculated value of the (t- cal) is greater than or equal to the critical value of (t-crit) at .05 level of significance, then reject the null hypothesis.

RESULT AND FINDINGS

Research Question 1: *What are the system design skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Mean Responses of Mean Responses of Electrical Industry Managers and Supervisors on the System Design Skills Required for Employability of Electrical Technology Education Graduates in the Industries

S/N	Items	Managers N=40		Supervisors N=40			
		\bar{x}	SD	RMK	\bar{x}	SD	RMK
	System Design Skills						
1.	Ability to design and analyze electrical circuits using software tools like SPICE	4.05	.783	Agree	4.09	.678	Agree
2.	Ability to develop embedded systems using microcontrollers, sensors, and actuators	4.10	.709	Agree	4.27	.517	Agree
3.	Ability to design and analyze control systems	4.23	.660	Agree	4.09	.522	Agree
4.	Ability to design communication systems	3.65	.700	Agree	4.12	.740	Agree
5.	Ability to design and analyze digital signal processing systems using techniques	4.08	.764	Agree	4.00	.791	Agree
6.	Ability to design and analyze thermal management systems	3.90	.744	Agree	3.94	.827	Agree
7.	Ability to design and develop HMIs using software tools like LabVIEW, Visual Studio	4.35	.622	Agree	4.12	.696	Agree
8.	Ability to design systems with manufacturability and assembly in mind	4.18	.675	Agree	4.12	.781	Agree
9.	Ability to carry out Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC) Design	4.08	.829	Agree	4.18	.683	Agree
10.	Ability to carry out Reliability and Maintainability Design	4.28	.987	Agree	4.00	.750	Agree
	Grand Mean	4.087	.1604	Agree	4.094	.1749	Agree

Table 1: is the result of the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system design skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria. The table revealed that the respondents agreed that the items in the table are required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries. The mean responses of the electrical industry managers ranged from 3.65 to 4.23 while the mean responses of the supervisors ranged from 3.94 to 4.27. The grand mean of electrical industry managers and supervisors were 4.087 and 4.094 respectively this exceeded the criterion mean of 3.50 thus the respondents agreed that system design skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria. The closeness of the standard deviation shows the homogeneity of the electrical industry managers and supervisors.

Research question 2: *What are the system installation skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria?*

Table 4.2: Mean Responses of Mean Responses of Electrical Industry Managers and Supervisors on the System Installation Skills Required for Employability of Electrical Technology Education Graduates in the Industries

S/N	Items		Managers N=40		RMK	Supervisors N=40		RMK
	System Skills	Installation	\bar{x}	SD		\bar{x}	SD	
1.	Ability to install solar panels		3.98	.733	Agree	3.85	.755	Agree
2.	Ability to install battery systems		3.78	1.000	Agree	3.88	.857	Agree
3.	Ability to test and commission electrical systems		3.70	1.159	Agree	3.70	.883	Agree
4.	Ability to install circuit breakers and fuses		3.60	1.008	Agree	3.82	1.103	Agree
5.	Ability to carry out Motor Installation and Alignment		3.63	.774	Agree	3.83	1.137	Agree
6.	Ability to install control systems, including PLCs, SCADA systems		3.88	.966	Agree	3.97	.918	Agree
7.	Ability to install power distribution systems		3.63	.868	Agree	3.58	.902	Agree
8.	Ability to understand grounding and bonding techniques		3.60	.982	Agree	3.50	.972	Agree
9.	Ability to install surge protection devices		4.03	1.000	Agree	3.91	.805	Agree
10.	Ability to understand electrical safety device installation techniques		3.58	.925	Agree	3.73	1.098	Agree
	Grand Mean		3.678	.2966	Agree	3.685	.2938	Agree

The data in Table 2 is the result of the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system installation skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria. The table revealed that the respondents agreed that the items in the table are required for employability of electrical technology education graduates in the industries. The mean responses of the electrical industry managers ranged from 3.60 to 4.03 while the mean responses of

the supervisors ranged from 3.50 to 4.10. The grand mean electrical industry managers and supervisors were 3.783 and 3.826 respectively this exceeded the criterion mean of 3.50 indicating that system installation skills are required for employability of electrical technology education graduates in the industries. The closeness of the standard deviation shows the homogeneity of the electrical industry managers and supervisors.

Research Question 3: *What are the system troubleshooting and maintenance skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria?*

Table 3: Mean Responses of Mean Responses of Electrical Industry Managers and Supervisors on the System Troubleshooting and Maintenance Skills Required for Employability of Electrical Technology Education Graduates in the Industries

S/N	System Troubleshooting and Maintenance Skills	Managers N=40			Supervisors N=40		
		\bar{X}	SD	RMK	\bar{X}	SD	RMK
1)	Ability to analyze reliability and maintainability data	3.73	.960	Agree	3.88	.927	Agree
2)	Ability to implement condition-based maintenance strategies	4.05	.639	Agree	3.88	.781	Agree
3)	Ability to implement TPM strategies	4.03	.698	Agree	3.91	.843	Agree
4)	Ability to troubleshoot EMC issues	4.18	.712	Agree	4.00	.750	Agree
5)	Ability to troubleshoot communication systems	4.28	.679	Agree	4.03	.728	Agree
6)	Ability to troubleshoot power systems	4.05	.749	Agree	4.00	.901	Agree
7)	Ability to measure and test electrical parameters like voltage	4.05	.677	Agree	3.97	.637	Agree
8)	Ability to analyze and troubleshoot electrical circuits using tools	3.98	.920	Agree	4.06	.609	Agree
9)	Ability to troubleshoot microcontrollers and embedded systems using tools like debuggers	4.10	.672	Agree	4.18	.635	Agree
10)	Ability to troubleshoot digital signal processing systems	4.13	.648	Agree	4.12	4.13	Agree
	Grand Mean	4.055	.1894	Agree	4.003	.1879	Agree

The data in Table 3: is the result of the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system troubleshooting and maintenance skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria. The table revealed that the respondents agreed with the items in the table as the system troubleshooting and maintenance skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries. The mean responses of the electrical industry managers ranged from 3.73 to 4.18 while the mean responses of the supervisors ranged from 3.88 to 4.18. The grand mean of electrical industry managers and supervisors were 4.055 and 4.003 respectively this exceeded the criterion mean of 3.50 thus the respondents agreed on the items in the questionnaire as the system troubleshooting and maintenance skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria. The closeness of the standard deviation shows the homogeneity of the electrical industry managers and supervisors.

Test of Hypothesis

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system design skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria

Table 4: t-test analysis on the Mean Response of Electrical Industry Managers and supervisors on System Design Skills Required for Employability of Electrical Technology Education Graduates in the Industries

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	T	Sig	P	Decision
Managers	50	4.087	.1604	72				Accept
Technicians	100	4.094	.1749					
					.870	.264	.05	

Table 4: is the result of an independent sample t-test comparing the mean responses between the mean response of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system design skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria. The data revealed that mean of electrical industry managers is 4.087 and a standard deviation. 1604. For supervisors the mean of 4.094 and a standard deviation of .1749 were obtained. The calculated t value is .870 since the significant value (2-tailed) of .264 exceeded .05 ($P > .05$) the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus there is no significant difference between the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system design skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system installation skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria

Table 5: t-test analysis on the Mean Response of Electrical Industry Managers and Supervisors on System Installation Skills Required for Employability of Electrical Technology Education Graduates in the Industries

Respondents	NO	\bar{X}	SD	Df	T	Sig	P	Decision
Managers	50	4.055	.1894	72				Accept
Technicians	100	4.003	.1879					
					.246	.599	.05	

Table 5 shows the result of an independent sample t-test which was conducted to compare the mean response of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system installation skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria. The data revealed that mean of electrical industry managers is 4.055 and a standard deviation. .1894. For supervisors the mean of 4.003 and a standard deviation of 1879 were obtained. The calculated t value is .246. Since the significant value (2-tailed) of .599 exceeded .05 ($P > .05$) the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus there is no significant difference between the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system installation skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria.

HO₃: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system troubleshooting and maintenance skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria

Table 6: t-test analysis on the Mean Response of Electrical Industry Managers and Supervisors on System Troubleshooting and Maintenance Skills Required for Employability of Electrical Technology Education Graduates in the Industries

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	T	Sig	P	Decision
Electrical Industry Managers	40	3.678	.2966	72				Accepted
Supervisors	40	3.685	.2938					
					.916	.689		

Table 6 shows the result of an independent sample t-test which was conducted to compare the mean response of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system troubleshooting and maintenance skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers

state, Nigeria. The data revealed that mean of electrical industry managers is 3.678 and a standard deviation. 2966. For supervisors the mean of 3.685 and a standard deviation of. 2938 were obtained. The calculated t value is .916. Since the significant value (2-tailed) of. 689 exceeded .05 ($P > .05$) the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus there is no significant difference between the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system troubleshooting and maintenance skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

Research Question 1 revealed that system design skills are required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria. This is also sustained with the result of the hypothesis in table 4 which revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system design skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria

Research Question 2: revealed that system installation skills are required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria, This is also sustained with the result of the hypothesis in table 5 which revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system installation skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria

Research Question 3: revealed that system troubleshooting and maintenance skills are required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria. This is also sustained with the result of the hypothesis in table 6 which revealed that Thus there is no significant difference between the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system troubleshooting and maintenance skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDING

Research Question 1: revealed that system design skills are required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria. While the result of hypotheses one in table 4 revealed that mean of electrical industry managers is 4.087 and a standard deviation. 1604. For supervisors the mean of 4.094 and a standard deviation of .1749 were obtained. The calculated t value is .870 since the significant value (2-tailed) of .264 exceeded .05 ($P > .05$) the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus there is no significant difference between the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system design skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria. The findings of the study is agreement with Minoli et al., (2017) who stated that continuous learning and adaptation in this rapidly evolving sector are essential for maintaining employability in Rivers State's industries.

Research Question 2: revealed that system installation skills are required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state. While the result of hypotheses two in table 5: revealed that revealed that mean of electrical industry managers is 4.055 and a standard deviation. .1894. For supervisors the mean of 4.003 and a standard deviation of 1879 were obtained. The calculated t value is .246. Since the significant value (2-tailed) of .599 exceeded .05 ($P > .05$) the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus there is no significant difference between the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system installation skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria. This finding is support by Kim et al., (2020), who affirmed that as industries increasingly prioritize secure energy management systems, knowledge of cybersecurity aspects related to BMS becomes an added advantage for graduates.

Research Question 3: revealed that system troubleshooting and maintenance skills are required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria. While the result of hypotheses three in table 6: showed that the mean of electrical industry managers is 3.678 and a standard deviation. 2966. For supervisors the mean of 3.685 and a standard deviation of. 2938 were obtained. The calculated t value is .916. Since the significant value (2-tailed) of. 689 exceeded .05

($P > .05$) the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus there is no significant difference between the mean responses of electrical industry managers and supervisors on the system troubleshooting and maintenance skills required for employability of Electrical Technology Education graduates in the industries in Rivers state, Nigeria. The findings is support with Ouramdane et al., (2021), who stated that, electrical technology graduates must acquire skills in energy dispatching and optimization techniques. Understanding the complexities involved in microgrid energy management will better prepare graduates to tackle contemporary energy challenges in Rivers State.

CONCLUSION

This study identified the essential energy management system skills required for Electrical Technology Education graduates to enhance their employability in Rivers State, Nigeria. The results emphasized the importance of system design, installation, and troubleshooting/maintenance skills in the industry. The findings have significant implications for educational institutions and industry stakeholders. Specifically, universities should revise their Electrical Technology Education curricula to ensure alignment with industry requirements, while fostering partnerships with industries to provide students with hands-on training and practical experience. Moreover, the study emphasizes the need for Electrical Technology Education graduates to engage in continuous professional development to remain competitive in the rapidly evolving energy sector. Ultimately, this research contributes to the existing body of knowledge on the skills required for employability in the energy sector, providing valuable insights for education and industry stakeholders.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Industries should provide opportunities for Electrical Technology Education students to gain practical experience in system troubleshooting and maintenance.
2. Universities offering Electrical Technology Education programs should review and revise their curricula to ensure that they are providing students with the necessary skills and knowledge in system design
3. Educational institutions offering Electrical Technology Education in rivers state should incorporate practical training and hands-on experience in energy management systems into their curricula.

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